

Determine the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type-2 diabetic patients

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this study was to determine the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type-2 diabetic patients.

Material and Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study conducted at Department of Cardiology, Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology, Faisalabad and Department of Internal Medicine of Allied Hospital Faisalabad. Study was carried out over a period of six months from 01-03-2022 to 01-09-2022. After approval from local ethical review committee, fulfilling the inclusion criteria were selected. As echocardiography is the gold standard to diagnose diastolic dysfunction so all the enrolled patients underwent echocardiography by consultant cardiologist and diastolic dysfunction (present/absent) was noted as mentioned in operational definition.

Results: Out of total 150 patients, 32.0 % (n=48) were in age group of 35-50 years and 68.0 % (n=102) were in age group of 51-60 years. There were 60.0% (n=90) male and 40.0% (n=60) females in our study. Mean age was 52.10±4.650 years. The number of rural populations was 31.3% (n=47) and 68.7% (n=103) urban population. Duration of diabetes was 3.17±1.430 years. And mean ejection fraction (EF) was 59.06±5.959. Frequency of diastolic dysfunction was found in 49.3 % (n=74).

Conclusion: In conclusion, our results indicate that asymptomatic DM type 2 has significantly high prevalence of diastolic dysfunction. Subjects with DM type 2 should be screened for sub clinical diastolic dysfunction by echocardiography.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, Diastolic dysfunction, Normotensive

How to cite: Akram MA, Asghar N, Abbas F, Akram M, Abbas S, Yasir M. Determine the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type-2 diabetic patients. *Esculapio-JSIMS* 2026;22(03): 187-191 **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20484788>

Introduction

Diabetes and cardiovascular diseases are rapidly growing pandemics. Globally, DM prevalence is about 463 million in 2019, representing 9.3% of the global adult population expected to increase to 578 million (10.2%) in 2030 and almost 700 million (10.9%) by 2045.¹ There is an undisputed bidirectional relationship between type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and cardiovascular disease (CVD) whereby the former heightens the risk of the latter.²

The prevalence of ischemic heart disease (IHD) is higher in diabetic patient as compared to general population.³ Diabetes mellitus is considered as a major risk factor for the development of diastolic dysfunction. Recent studies have demonstrated that the incidence of diastolic dysfunction in diabetic patients is about 30-75%.⁴ Diastolic dysfunction is defined as a disturbance in ventricular relaxation, distensibility or filling regardless of normal or reduced ejection fraction (EF), which results in development of diastolic heart failure (DHF).⁵ The presence of myocardial dysfunction in diabetic patients in the absence of ischemic, valvular or hypertensive heart disease has been termed as “diabetic cardiomyopathy”.^{4, 5} It has been described that an early sign of the diabetic cardiomyopathy is diastolic dysfunction that may proceed to the systolic damage.⁶ Thus diastolic dysfunction may represent the earliest stage of diabetic cardiomyopathy and timely diagnosis of this entity can be vital in the management of patients. So far, very few population-based studies have been carried out to demonstrate the prevalence of diastolic dysfunction among

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Submission Date: 11-09-2025

1st Revision Date: 21-11-2025

Acceptance Date: 23-02-2026

diabetic subjects.⁷

Fawad et al conducted a study to determine the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type-2 diabetics on 150 consecutive patients with type-2 diabetes mellitus having normal blood pressure and normal resting electrocardiogram and without any symptoms of heart failure. Amongst them, 93 (62%) were males and 57(38%) were females. Mean age was 46.26±8.096 years. Of the total, 72 (48%) patients were found to have diastolic dysfunction and 78 (52%) patients did not have diastolic dysfunction.⁸

The rationale of the study is to see the occurrence of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic, normotensive type-2 diabetic patients as diastolic dysfunction may represent the first stage of diabetic cardiomyopathy. So, the patients might be assessed early and hence early treatment of diastolic function at asymptomatic stage in individuals with diabetes might be started.

Material and Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional study conducted at Department of Cardiology, Faisalabad Institute of Cardiology, Faisalabad and Department of Internal Medicine of Allied Hospital Faisalabad. Study was carried out over a period of six months from 01-03-2022 to 01-09-2022. After approval from local ethical review committee, fulfilling the inclusion criteria were selected. As echocardiography is the gold standard to diagnose diastolic dysfunction so all the enrolled patients underwent echocardiography by consultant cardiologist and diastolic dysfunction (present/absent) was noted as mentioned in operational definition. Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus having normal blood pressure, normal resting electrocardiogram and without any symptoms of heart failure like dyspnea. Age: 35-60 years. Both genders. Patients having segmental wall motion defects and valvular heart disease on Doppler echocardiography. Patients having BP > 130/85 or taking any antihypertensive medication. Patients with left ventricular hypertrophy on ECG or patients with left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) on echocardiography. Patients with serum creatinine >1.5mg/dl. Patients with T2DM diagnosed for more than 10 years. Patient of restrictive cardiomyopathy or constrictive pericarditis. Known case of ischemic heart disease. As echocardiography is the gold standard to diagnose diastolic dysfunction so on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria, all the enrolled patients according to age, gender, duration of DM, rural or urban background, were underwent echocardiography by consultant cardiologist and diastolic dysfunction (present/absent) was noted as mentioned in operational definition. All this data was recorded on a predesigned Performa (Annexure-I).

All the data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS version 25.0. The quantitative variables like age,

duration of diabetes and ejection fraction (EF) were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables like gender, place of living and presence of diastolic dysfunction (yes/no) were presented as frequency and percentage. Effect modifiers like age, gender, place of living and duration of diabetes were controlled by stratification. Post-stratification chi square test was applied and P-value ≤ 0.05 was considered as significant.

Results

Total of 150 patients fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected to determine the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type 2 diabetic patients. Age distribution of the patients was done, it showed that out of 150 patients, 32.0 % (n=48) were in age group of 35-50 years and 68.0 % (n=102) were in age group of 51-60 years. Mean age was calculated as 52.10±4.650 years. (Table No. 1). Distribution of duration of diabetes was 3.17±1.430 years. (Table No. 2). Distribution of Ejection fraction (EF) was 59.06±5.959. (Table No. 3). Total of 100 patients, 60.0% (n=90) were male and 40.0% (n=60) females. (Table No. 4). Total of 100 patients, 31.3% (n=47) were rural population and 68.7% (n=103) urban population (Table No. 5). Frequency of diastolic dysfunction was 49.3 % (n=74). (Table No. 6). The data was stratified for age, gender, place of living and duration of diabetes shown in Table No. 7-10 respectively.

Table 1: Stratification for diastolic dysfunction with respect to age using chi-square test

Age group	Diastolic dysfunction		Total	p value
	Present	Absent		
35-50 years	28 58.3%	20 41.7%	48 100.0%	0.130
51-60 years	46 45.1%	56 54.9%	102 100.0%	
Total	74 49.3%	76 50.7%	150 100.0%	

Table 2: Stratification for diastolic dysfunction with respect to gender using chi-square test

Gender	Diastolic dysfunction		Total	p value
	Present	Absent		

Male	43	47	90	0.641
	47.8%	52.2%	100.0%	
Female	31	29	60	
	51.7%	48.3%	100.0%	
Total	74	76	150	
	49.3%	50.7%	100.0%	

Table 3: Stratification for diastolic dysfunction with respect to place of living using chi-square test

Place of living	Diastolic dysfunction		Total	p value
	Present	Absent		
Rural	23	24	47	0.948
	48.9%	51.1%	100.0%	
Urban	51	52	103	
	49.5%	50.5%	100.0%	
Total	74	76	150	
	49.3%	50.7%	100.0%	

In current study, out of 150 patients, 32.0 % (n=48) were in age group of 35-50 years and 68.0 % (n=102) were in age group of 51-60 years. Mean age was 52.10±4.650 years. Distribution of duration of diabetes was 3.17±1.430 years. And Ejection fraction (EF) was 59.06±5.959. There were 60.0% (n=90) male and 40.0% (n=60) females in our study. The number of rural population was 31.3% (n=47) and 68.7% (n=103) urban population. Frequency of diastolic dysfunction in was 49.3 % (n=74).

Discussion

The incidence of diabetes mellitus (DM) is increasing worldwide and rapidly assuming epidemic proportions. Over the last three decades, a number of epidemiological, clinical and autopsy studies have proposed the presence of diabetic heart disease as a distinct clinical entity. Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) is also

referred to as HF, with preserved left ventricular systolic function. Many studies have reported that the incidence of heart failure in diabetic subjects is high even in the absence of hypertension and coronary artery disease. Studies have reported a high prevalence of pre-clinical diastolic dysfunction among subjects with DM.⁹ The evidence indicates that myocardial damage in diabetic subjects affects diastolic function before the systolic function. The pathogenesis of this left ventricular (LV) dysfunction in diabetic subjects is not clearly understood.

Diabetic cardiomyopathy has been proposed as an independent cardiovascular disease, and many mechanisms, such as microvascular disease, autonomic dysfunction, metabolic disorders, and interstitial fibrosis, have been suggested as causative factors.¹⁰ However, the exact etio-pathogenesis of diabetic cardiomyopathy still remains unclear.

In another study done by Patil, et.al. they reveal high burden of diastolic dysfunction in cohort of type 2 DM population. In their present prospective case control study, 127 subjects with type-2 DM as cases; and, 100 healthy subjects as controls, were included. Overall mean of obesity indices like BMI, WC and WHR were significantly higher in subjects with type 2 DM compared to the control group. Mean of fasting BSL, HbA1c, serum TC, serum TG and LDL cholesterol in case group was significantly higher as compared to the control group. The mean of HDL cholesterol was lower in the case group as compared to the control group. Total 69 (54.33%) subjects from the case group had diastolic dysfunction, and 11 (11%) amongst control group showed the diastolic dysfunction. Diastolic dysfunction in type -2 diabetes subjects was significantly higher as compared to the control group (*P* < 0.001). E/A ratio negatively correlated with age, WC, WHR, duration of DM, HbA1c level, fasting BSL, and serum TG levels; and, positively correlated with serum HDL- cholesterol. E/e' ratio positively correlated with age, WC, WHR, duration of DM, HbA1c level, fasting BSL, and serum TG levels; and, negatively correlated with serum HDL- cholesterol. Duration of diabetes mellitus of 11 to 15 years had more prevalence of diastolic dysfunction (*P* < 0.02). Subjects with high WC and high WHR had statistically significant diastolic dysfunction. Subjects with HbA1c > 7.5% had more prevalence of diastolic dysfunction than subjects with HbA1c < 7.5% (*P* < 0.02). Diastolic dysfunction was significantly high in patient with age > 45 years compared to age < 45 years (*P* < 0.05). Diastolic dysfunction was present in majority of the subjects with autonomic neuropathy and retinopathy.¹¹

Masugata ET AL.¹² in their case control study of 77 normotensive patients found that, the cardiac diastolic dysfunction without LV systolic dysfunction in patients with well-controlled type 2 DM is related neither to hypertension nor LV hypertrophy, but rather to aging and the duration of

type 2 DM. Similarly, in the present study, total 54.33% of subjects from case group without hypertension and CAD had diastolic dysfunction with normal LV systolic function. Annonu ET AL.¹³ in their case control study of 66 subjects found that there was an inverse correlation between the duration of diabetes and E/A ratio ($r = -0.4$, 'P' <.005). E/A ratio < 1 was associated with a higher prevalence of retinopathy (49% versus 20%, 'p'0 =0.01) and abnormal blood pressure response to standing (29% versus 4%, 'P' <.005). LV systolic and diastolic abnormalities are correlated with the duration of diabetes and with other diabetic micro-angiopathies, such as diabetic retinopathy and neuropathy.

Mishra ET AL. in their case control study of 71 subjects with type 2 DM found that asymptomatic diabetic patients have reduced LV systolic and diastolic function as compared with healthy subjects. LV systolic and diastolic abnormalities are correlated with the duration of diabetes and with diabetic microangiopathies, like retinopathy and neuropathy.¹⁴

From ET AL.¹⁵ in their study of 484 subjects between 1996 to 2007 year found that a duration of diabetes ≥ 4 years was independently associated with LV diastolic dysfunction ($E/e' > 15$) with odds ratio 1.91. Doppler imaging velocity of the medial mitral annulus during passive filling (E/e') ratio in diabetic patients is associated with the subsequent development of HF and increased mortality. Similarly in our study, duration of diabetes 11-15 years had more prevalence of diastolic dysfunction as compared to the 6-10-year group ('P' < 0.02). Sohail ET AL.¹⁶ in their study of 212 diabetic population found that 30.76% patients with type-2 DM had diastolic dysfunction. The LV diastolic dysfunction is much more prevalent in patients with type-2 diabetes mellitus and LV diastolic dysfunction is an early marker of diabetic cardiomyopathy. In our study, prevalence of type 2 DM was 54.33%.

Schannwell ET AL. in their study population of 87 subjects concluded that even young subjects with diabetes mellitus suffer from a diastolic dysfunction, while systolic ventricular function is normal. From the above discussion and comparison of present study findings with various studies, we found that there was high prevalence of diastolic dysfunction in subjects with asymptomatic type 2 DM.¹⁷

Conclusion

In current study we determined the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type 2 diabetic patients. We found that the frequency of diastolic dysfunction in was 49.3 % (n=74). In conclusion, our results indicate that asymptomatic type 2 DM has significantly high prevalence of diastolic dysfunction. Subjects with DM type 2 should be screened for sub clinical diastolic dysfunction by echocardiography.

Funding source: None

Conflict of interest: None

References

1. Saeedi P, Petersohn I, Salpea P, Malanda B, Karuranga S, Unwin N, et al. Global and regional diabetes prevalence estimates for 2019 and projections for 2030 and 2045: Results from the International Diabetes Federation Diabetes Atlas, 9th edition. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2019;157:107843
2. Kenny H, Abel E. Heart failure in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Circ Res.* 2019;124:121-41.
3. Einarson T, Acs A, Ludwig C, Panton UH. Prevalence of cardiovascular disease in type 2 diabetes: a systematic literature review of scientific evidence from across the world in 2007-2017. *Cardiovasc Diabetol.* 2018;17:83.
4. Chaturvedi M, Maheshwari PK, Javed M, Pandey A, Baiswar R. Assessment of diastolic dysfunction among asymptomatic type 2 diabetes mellitus patients using 2-D echocardiography and tissue doppler imaging. *J Indian Acad Clin Med.* 2018;19(2):92-5.
- 5.
6. Elburki ARF, Patil R, Amgrab EA. Assessment of diastolic dysfunction in normotensive asymptomatic type II diabetes mellitus and correlation with pulmonary artery pressure. *Int J Res Rev.* 2020;7:8-13
7. Newman JD, Schwartzbard AZ, Weintraub HS, Goldberg IJ, Berger JS. Primary prevention of cardiovascular disease in diabetes mellitus. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2017;70:883-93.
8. Raghoshma S, Rao A. Revelation of subclinical left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus using 2016 ASE/ EACVI guidelines. *Caspian J Intern Med* 2021;12(4):586-92
9. Randhawa FA, Hussnain MT, Nazir S, Faisal Masud F. Frequency of diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic normotensive type-2 diabetic patients. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad.* 2014;26:35-7.
10. Kazik A, Wilczek K, Poloński L. Management of diastolic heart failure. *Cardiol J.* 2010;17:558-65.
11. From AM, Scott CG, Chen HH. Changes in diastolic dysfunction in diabetes mellitus over time. *Am J Cardiol.* 2009;103:1463-6.

12. Patil VC, Patil HV, Shah KB, Vasani JD, Shetty P. Diastolic dysfunction in asymptomatic type 2 diabetes mellitus with normal systolic function. *J Cardiovasc Dis Res.* 2011 Oct;2(4):213-22.
13. Masugata H, Senda S, Goda F, Yoshihara Y, Yoshikawa K, Fujita N, et al. Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction in normotensive diabetic patients in various age strata. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2008;79:91–6.
14. Annonu AK, Fattah AA, Mokhtar MS, Ghareeb S, Elhendy A. Left ventricular systolic and diastolic functional abnormalities in asymptomatic patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *J Am Soc Echocardiogr.* 2001;14:885–91.
15. Mishra TK, Rath PK, Mohanty NK, Mishra SK. Left ventricular systolic and diastolic dysfunction and their relationship with microvascular complications in normotensive, asymptomatic patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Indian Heart J.* 2008;60:548–53.
16. From AM, Scott CG, Chen HH. Changes in diastolic dysfunction in diabetes mellitus over time. *Am J Cardiol.* 2009;103:1463–6.
17. Ashraf SM, Basir F. Association of hypertension and diastolic dysfunction with type-2 diabetes mellitus. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2007;23:344–8.
18. Schannwell CM, Schneppenheim M, Perings S, Plehn G, Strauer BE, Strauer Left ventricular diastolic dysfunction as an early manifestation of diabetic cardiomyopathy. *Cardiology.* 2002;98:33–9.

Author's contribution:

MAA, AN: Conceptualization of Project

AF, FA: Data Collection

AM, MAA: Literature Search

FA: Statistical Analysis

AF, FA: Drafting, Revision

MAA: Writing of Manuscript

